

Micro Small and Medium Industrial Scenario in Maharashtra State

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Abstract:

Maharashtra has been in the forefront in sustaining industrial growth and in creating environment conducive to industrial development. Investment – friendly industrial policies, excellent infrastructure and a strong and productive human resource base have made it a favorable destination for manufacturing, export and financial service sectors. The State Governments and other Stakeholders, through providing support to existing enterprises, adopting cutting edge technologies and encouraging creation of new enterprises. The Ministry of MSME runs various schemes aimed at financial assistance, technology assistance and up gradation infrastructure development, skill development and training, enhancing competitiveness and market assistance of MSMEs. The State continued to attract highest industrial proposals resulting into maximum generation of employment compared to other States due to availability of better infrastructure, skilled human resources and stable social conditions. The State's share in proposed investment and employment in the country is 10 and 15 percent respectively.

Keywords: MSMEs, Industrial Growth, Investment, Govt. Schemes, Employment Generation.

Introduction:

The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector has emerged as a highly vibrant and dynamic sector of the Indian economy over the last five decades. It contributes

significantly in the economic and social development of the country by fostering entrepreneurship and generating large employment opportunities at comparatively lower capital cost, next only to agriculture. MSMEs are complementary to large industries as ancillary units and this sector contributes significantly in the inclusive industrial development of the country. The MSMEs are widening their domain across sectors of the economy, producing diverse range of products and services to meet demands of domestic as well as global markets. Industrial sector in Maharashtra can be divided into three major parts i.e. micro industries, small industries and medium industries. Including all these three the sector is known as MSME – Micro Small Medium Enterprises sector. The researcher has in this sector studied the overall development of this sector in Maharashtra state with reference to present scenario. Since 1985, the Indian Government initiated a series of Liberalization aimed at Modernization of the manufacturing sector, improving the export performance and achieving a higher level of efficiency in the economy. The external liberalization consisted mainly of liberalized imports of technology, raw materials, spare parts, machinery and foreign equity participation.

This process of liberalization has gathered momentum from the beginning of 1990s. In the country the New Industrial Policy (NIP) 1991, has come into existence to direct towards improving the competitiveness of Indian industries and thereby increasing the exports of the country.

Maharashtra is India's leading industrial State contributing more than 20% in net value added in the organized manufacturing sector in the country. Almost 46% of the GSDP is contributed by industry. Major industries in Maharashtra include chemical and allied products, electrical and non-electrical machinery, textiles, petroleum and allied products. Other important industries include metal products, wine, jewellery, pharmaceuticals, engineering goods, machine tools, steel and iron casting and plastic wares etc.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the growth of MSME in the Maharashtra state
2. To study the impact of MSME an employment generation in the state
3. To study the emerging trends of MSMEs in Maharashtra state

Research Methodology and Sources of Data

The present study is purely based on the secondary data. The researcher has been collected required data for the analysis from different issues and references are collected from the Library sources which have supposed to be most reliable and authentic. Other hand internet and reputed publications has been widely used for the

collection of data.

Review of Literature

Das, S. K (2014) has stressed on the Entrepreneurship Development is prime base for fighting against an unemployment and mitigate poverty other hand to achieve overall socio-economic growth in our state.

Bilas. S Kale (2015) In his research paper entitle' Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

– A Case Study of Maharashtra' found that, there is growth of MSMEs continuously in the state. He also focused on an economic growth achieve by extending MSME units at large.

Md Riyazuddin khan, Abdulla (2019) the researchers has stated that, the MSMEs instrument is an important for economic growth and social development in developing countries like India. This study is an attempt to focus on the technical efficiency (TE) of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) enterprise sugar mills in Maharashtra andUttar Pradesh.

Boateng, K. Naveem, S., Nagaraju, Y. (2019) It is found that, the all states and union territories have their share of the MSMEs, the states of Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal followed by Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Rajasthan, and Madhya Pradesh, are the 10 states with the highest number of MSMEs. The findings again indicated that, MSMEs that engage in trade activities dominate the industry. It also found, the 51% of Indian MSMEs operates from the rural areas whereas 49% operates from the urban cities. The consistent growth of India's economy cannot be mentioned without acknowledging the contribution of the MSMEs. The MSMEs sector contributes as much as between 40 and

50 per cent of India's total export.

S. Manikandan the researcher has focused on the emerging MSMEs and start-ups which have created new market in India along with young entrepreneurs to start various enterprises. Also in his research paper found that, the young entrepreneurs shown interests in service sector business with help of governments of India's start-ups make in India initiative.

Krishna Kumar (2003) He has stressed on the technological transfer and innovative ideas which involves important. The researcher has been highlighted on MSME's single handed deeds to streamline MSME's work regulated by MSME ministry of India.

Industrial Growth in Maharashtra:

Industrial sector in Maharashtra generally we can be divided into three major parts i.e. Micro Industries, Small Industries and Medium Industries, all these three the sector is known as MSME – Micro Small Medium Enterprises sector. The researcher has studied on this sector about the overall development of this sector in Maharashtra state. The researcher has shown as following.

Micro Industries in Maharashtra

Micro industries are the foremost and significant role playing in terms of self-employment creation specifically in rural and semi-urban areas. For the development of MSME, i.e. Micro and Small Enterprises, the Government of India has given importance in its MSME Development Act, 2006, for development of skills entrepreneurs and their employees, management of enterprises, technology up gradation, marketing assistance, infrastructure facilities, cluster development and delayed payment. The position of micro industries has shown in the table no.1

Table no.1
Micro Industries scenario from 2007 to March 2014

Sr No.	Name of District	Micro	Small	Medium	Total
1	Mumbai Suburban	5055	3751	101	8907
2	Mumbai Greater	1903	1370	28	3301
	Konkan Region	9825	8860	247	18932
3	Thane	6894	7681	189	14764
4	Raigad	1478	999	49	2526
5	Ratnagiri	701	124	5	830
6	Sindhudurgt	752	56	4	812
	Nasik Region	8320	2719	70	11109
7	Nasik	3869	1336	43	5248
8	Dhule	745	209	8	962
9	Nandurbar	123	142		265

10	Jalgaon	1637	405	7	2049
11	Ahmednagar	1946	627	12	2585
	Aurangabad Region	4681	1619	28	6328
12	Aurangabad	1444	706	17	2167
13	Jalna	257	138	9	404
14	Parbhani	349	76	0	425
15	Hingoli	163	139	0	302
16	Beed	797	118	0	915
17	Nanded	722	247	0	969
18	Osmanabad	215	36	0	251
19	Latur	734	159	2	895
	Pune Region	28508	9080	197	37785
20	Pune	13344	4397	130	17871
21	Sangli	2385	809	12	3206

22	Satara	1318	365	15	1698
23	Solapur	2729	411	3	3143
24	Kolhapur	8732	3098	37	11867
	Amravati Region	2536	408	05	2949
25	Buldhana	230	85	3	318
26	Akola	578	112	1	691
27	Washim	186	17	1	204
28	Amravati	789	106	0	895
29	Yevatmal	753	88	0	841
	Nagpur Region	8688	1828	59	10317
30	Nagpur	5246	1503	47	6796
31	Wardha	531	82	4	917
32	Bhandara	535	63	3	601
33	Gondia	611	41	1	653
34	Chandrapur	1174	112	13	1289
35	Gadchiroli	591	27	1	619
	Total	69516	29635	735	99628

Source: Directorate of Industries

From the above table no table no.1 is stated that, the number of total MSME registered end of the year march 2014. The researcher has focused on the new emerging industries in the Maharashtra it has

increased registration of MSMEs in end of March 2015. Therefore, the Government of India has declared procurement policy in the year 2012 and its given importance to MSME development act 2006.

Table No.2
Cluster/region wise distribution of MSMEs

Districts	Micro	Small	Medium	Total
Mumbai Suburban	5055	3751	101	8907
Mumbai Greater	1903	1370	28	3301
Konkan Region	9825	8860	247	18932
Nasik Region	8320	2719	70	11109
Pune Region	28508	9080	197	37785
Aurangabad	4681	1619	28	6328
Amravati Region	2536	408	5	2949
Nagpur Region	8688	1828	59	10575

Source: Directorate of Industries

From the above table no 2 and graph region wise MSMEs are shown, it is found that, the majority of industries existed and pulled towards Mumbai, Mumbai suburban Pune, Nasik and Nagpur, Aurangabad respectively. Pune –Mumbai industrial belt has grown rapidly as industrial development concern i.e more than 50 percent industries are only Pune and Mumbai, Konkan region (19%), Nasik (11%) and Nagpur (11%) respectively in the state.

Conclusion:

Maharashtra industrial development has happen such areas where there is availability of good infrastructure and access for transportation. Mumbai, the business capital of India, houses the headquarters of almost all major banks, financial institutions, insurance companies and mutual funds in India. The principal industrial zone in Maharashtra is the Mumbai-Thane-Pune belt, accounting for almost 60% of the State's output. Efforts are being made to promote other industrial areas like Nagpur, Aurangabad, Sholapur, Jalgaon, Amravati and Ratnagiri by building the necessary infrastructure and creating an environment for industrial development.

MSMEs has very crucial role for an employment generation in rural and semi-urban area along with having opportunity to entre new young entrepreneurs to start-up business with innovative ideas and technology.

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